

RISK FACTORS OF CARDIOVASCULAR DISEASE AND ITS EFFECTS ON OBESITY IN PATIENTS OF QUETTA DISTRICT, BALOCHISTAN, PAKISTAN

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Abstract

The study, which examined the occurrence of cutaneous leishmaniasis in people living in Tehsil Muslim Bagh's districts, was conducted between September 2018 and April 2019. Blood samples and skin lesions were used to identify positive cases after suspects were screened for the illness. Samples were mounted so that their trace could be seen. 207 individuals of various ages and sexes were examined in total, however, only 192 (92%) of the suspected cases had the illness verified. Male cases made up 64% of all cases, a large percentage. Compared to other groups, the lesion was found more commonly (31%) in young people aged 21 to 30. Legs were found to be more infected in both sexes than arms (20% male + 0% female), cheeks (15% male + 11% female), or arms (45% male + 20% female). The least infected bodily parts included (4% in males + 5% in females) in the mixed group. In conclusion, Cutaneous Leishmaniasis was most prevalent in District East (23.2% male + 8.8% female), followed by District West (10.7% male + 4.3% female), District Central (6.8% male + 5.2% female), District (Nisai) (4.4% male + 6.6% female), and District South (3.8% male + 4.2% female), according to samples from various villages in the Muslim Bagh region.

KEYWORDS: Risk Factors, Cardiovascular Disease, Cutaneous Leishmaniasis.

INTRODUCTION

The protozoan illness known as cutaneous leishmaniasis is brought on by the parasite *Leishmania* and is spread by the bite of a female sand fly. These organisms are usually found in individuals with immune system suppression and are prevalent in endemic regions in people along with the suitable sand fly vectors (Varikuti et al.,2018). There are about 20 species of *Leishmania* that are well recognized and have the potential to infect humans. These organisms are in charge of three distinct clinical diseases and the three types of leishmaniasis are cutaneous, mucocutaneous, and abdominal (CL) (Nieva et al., 2021). According to WHO (2017), the maximum severely impacted nations by Cutaneous Leishmaniasis include Pakistan, Afghanistan, Albania, etc. (Khan et al.,2021).

Leishmaniasis is just one of the many skin conditions that pose a constant danger to Pakistan. Sadly, until a seismic eruption was noticed in Quetta in 1935, there was no real evidence of leishmaniasis in Pakistan (Yousuf et al, 2021). The northern mountainous area provided the first report of it in 1996. Since then, 20,000 cases are recorded annually. The two Sindh regions of Dadu and Larkana recorded the largest outbreaks, totaling 11,000 cases. Nearly all of Pakistan's regions have the highest prevalence of cutaneous leishmaniasis (Inceboz 2019).

This disease frequently affects the world's poorest individuals. Leishmaniasis is a serious issue in the Eastern Mediterranean (WHO, 2019). The illness is reportedly a vector-borne one and reported in 88 nations worldwide, of which 16 are developed, 13 are among the least evolved of the 72 developing countries. The seven nations of Syria, Saudi Arabia, Afghanistan, Algeria, Brazil, Iran, and Peru accounted for more than 90% of all CL instances. The (WHO) estimates that CL affects close to 1.2 billion people worldwide and that 5–20 lakh new cases are diagnosed each year (Nawaz et al., 2020).

Leishmaniasis is more common than ever, and several man-made variables, such as migration, deforestation, urbanization, and immunosuppression are to blame (Hong et al., 2020). According to a 2010 WHO study, Pakistan is home to three different species of cutaneous leishmaniasis. *Leishmania tropica* is responsible for *Leishmania major* and *Leishmania infantum* are the causes of zoonotic cutaneous leishmaniasis (ZCL) and zoonotic visceral leishmaniasis (ZVL), whereas anthroponotic cutaneous leishmaniasis (ACL) is caused by both of these parasites respectively (Ghatee, Taylor & Karamian 2020).

Papatasi sergenti and people, respectively, are *Leishmania tropica*'s carrier and basin. *Leishmania major* is carried by the Great gerbil (*Rhombomys opimus*) and the Indian desert gerbil, whereas *Leishmania infantum* has a canine repository and an unknown vector.

Cutaneous leishmaniasis is prevalent almost the entire length of Pakistan, from Karachi, through KPK, FATA, Punjab, Sindh, and Baluchistan (Ayaz et al., 2018). The goal of the current study is to compile information on cutaneous leishmaniasis prevalence and treatment options in six areas of Karachi, one of the biggest global towns.

Several factors can raise the danger of developing cutaneous leishmaniasis. These comprise living in or traveling to an endemic area, particularly if protective measures are not taken to prevent sand fly bites. Poor housing conditions and poverty may also increase the risk, as these factors can contribute to more people being exposed to sand flies (Amane et al., 2022). Additionally, those who have compromised immune systems, such as those who have HIV/AIDS or are enduring chemotherapy, are more likely to contract the illness.

Depending on the *Leishmania* species involved and the immune response of the person, cutaneous leishmaniasis can manifest with a variety of symptoms. A skin lesion, which typically appears at the location of the sand fly bite, is the most common symptom but can also manifest elsewhere on the body. A tiny, painless bump or nodule that occasionally develops into a lesion that may eventually ulcerate and become an open sore with a raised edge. The lesion may be surrounded by redness and inflammation, and may be accompanied by fever, malaise, and other symptoms (Silveira ET AL., 2009).

Alvar et al. (2012) estimated that the number of new instances of cutaneous leishmaniasis in the world in 2010 ranged between 0.7 million and 1.2 million. The countries with the highest disease loads were Afghanistan, Algeria etc. A study showed in Iran by Khosravi et al. (2017) found that the overall cutaneous leishmaniasis was prevalent nearly 15.5% in the study population. Risk factors for infection included being male, living in rural areas, having a family history of the disease, and having a history of previous leishmaniasis.

Amin et al., (2012) by thorough study and meta-analysis showed that cutaneous leishmaniasis was present in the Middle East at a prevalence of 5.5%. With the highest occurrence observed in Iran (17.8%) and Saudi Arabia (16.3%). Risk factors for infection included living in rural areas, having a low socioeconomic status, and having visited common regions in the past. Al-Ani et al., (2018) found that the prevalence of cutaneous leishmaniasis was 1.5% in the study population. Risk factors for infection included living in rural areas, having a history of previous leishmaniasis, and having visited prevalent regions in the past.

According to Neira et al., (2022), that 6.7% of people had cutaneous leishmaniasis, according to inspection study population. Risk factors for infection included living in rural areas, having a history of previous leishmaniasis.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A cross-sectional study or investigation relying on surveys was accompanied on the Frequency and Hazard factors of cutaneous leishmaniasis in tehsil Muslim Bagh district Killa Saifullah, Balochistan, Pakistan. The area of district Muslim Bagh (Killa- Saifullah) is 6831km² having a population of 342,814 as of 2017 census. A joint clinical research committee of Bolan Medical Complex and University of Balochistan, Quetta, ethically authorized the study, which was conducted between July 2022 and September 2022 in accordance with the Helsinki Declarations for Human Experiments.

A total of 207 suspected patients with active lesions who frequented the DHQ facility in Muslim Bagh were clinically examined. A pre-made proforma was filled out with information about the patient's name, father's name, sex, age, profession lesions' location and quantity, when the disease's first symptoms appeared, previous medical history, address, ethnicity, and treatments, and prior diagnoses made using microscopic examination and/or biopsy tests. The patient was interviewed face-to-face to collect information about a number of different factors. Digital cameras or mobile phones were used to capture pictures of the lesion.

2.1. Statistical analysis

The Microsoft Office Excel Suite 2007® was used for the statistical study. When there were notable differences, the Student T-test was used. The importance threshold for modifications between men and females, as well as between age groups, infected body parts, and geographic regions, was set at p 0.05.

2.2. Blood and skin biopsy samples are collected

2.2.1. Samples of Biopsy

Samples of skin lesions were gathered with obvious symptoms of skin illness. Before gathering, 100% ethanol was used to clean and sterilize the cutaneous lesions. Between the hand and the first finger, the lesions were punctured. Using a sterile blood lancet, skin scrape samples were collected from the lesion's punctured border and put on one side of the slide. The examination slide had a thick smear on one surface that was fixed in 100% methanol for 30 minutes. Using a permanent marker, the transparencies were stamped with a serial number.

Figure No.1: Samples Taken During Biopsies from Various Bodily Regions

2.2.2. Samples of Blood

Peripheral blood was cautiously injected into the test container using a syringe. The drawn blood samples were spun at a speed of 3000 for 30 minutes. A pipette was used to apply the Buffy coat lightly to the test plates before being immersed in 100% methanol for 30 minutes to repair them. The images were permitted to stain and after air dry before being gently washed with water.

Figure No.2: Blood Samples Taken from Various Body Regions of Infection Sites

2.2.3. Staining and microscopy-based detection

Giemsa-stained skin biopsies and direct parasite detection in impression smears can both be used to identify cutaneous leishmaniasis (Minnat & Al-Bassam 2018). Working Giemsa stain was used for 30 minutes on slides of blood and skin lesions from ill individuals that are dry, thin, and fixed. After staining, the slides were carefully rinsed with water, air dried, and then dried once more. To detect protozoan parasites, the slides were examined with a lens and an oil immersion objective (10 x 100 magnifications) (Leishman Donovan bodies). Leishman-Donovan (LD) corpses discovered in the smear were considered to be reliable proof.

3. RESULTS

Among the 207 inhabitants of the different Villages in Muslim Bagh, to determine the prevalence of cutaneous leishmaniasis, a study or investigation on the prevalence and risk factors of cutaneous leishmaniasis was carried out in the district Muslim Bagh (Killa-Saifullah), Balochistan, Pakistan. In the research, a total of 207 individuals were screened; 192 individuals (or 92.75% of the total) tested positive for Cutaneous Leishmaniasis, with 64% of the males (n = 123) and 36% of the females (n = 69) infected shown in Table. 1 and Figure.1.

Table No.1: Occurrence of Cutaneous Leishmaniasis in Gender Wise

Leishmaniasis based on Gender Wise					
Sex	Male	Female	Total	Male %	Female %
Patient's Number	35	20	55	64%	36%

Figure No.3: Occurrence of Cutaneous Leishmaniasis in Gender Wise

They were 0 to 70 years old. The year starting on the day of birth is indicated by the zero. According to Table 2 and Figure 2, the age group of 21 to 30 years had the greatest prevalence of Cutaneous Leishmaniasis at 31%, followed by 10 to 19 years at 22%, then zero to ten years at 20%, then 30 to 39 years at 13%, and the age groups of 50 to 59 years at 7%.

Table No.2: Incidence of Cutaneous Leishmaniasis in Age Wise

Age	Male	Female	Total	Male Percent	Female Percent
0-9	6	5	11	11%	9%
10-19	7	5	12	13%	9%
20-29	13	4	17	24%	7%
30-39	5	2	7	9%	4%
40-49	1	3	4	2%	5%
50-59	3	1	4	5%	2%
60-69	0	0	0	0%	0%

Figure No.4: Incidence of Cutaneous Leishmaniasis in Age Wise

Both genders' exposed bodily parts were discovered to be heavily infected. Forehead (15.3% male, 10.9% female), mixed bodily parts (4.4% male, 4.8% female), and arms (20% male, 0% female) had the lowest percentages of infections. Legs had the highest percentage of infections (24.8% male, 19.8% female) (Table. 3 and Figure.3).

Table No.3: Body Sections Wise Prevalence of Cutaneous Leishmaniasis

Body sites	Male	Female	Total	Male %	Female %
Face	8	6	14	15%	11%
Arms	11	0	11	20%	0%
Legs	14	11	25	25%	20%
Mixed	2	3	5	4%	5%

Figure No.5: Body Sections Wise Prevalence of Cutaneous Leishmaniasis

The majority of the lesions on each patient's body were on exposed areas like the hands, forehead, ankle, arm, ear, and legs. On their legs, limbs, and face, just one patient had more than thirty ulcerative lesions ranging in quantity from one to eight (1-8) lesions on each patient.

According to samples from various villages in the Muslim Bagh region, District East had the highest prevalence rate of Cutaneous Leishmaniasis (23.2% male + 8.8% female), followed by District West (10.7% male + 4.3% female), District Central (6.8% male + 5.2% female), District (Nisai) (4.4% male + 6.6% female), and District South (3.8% male + 4.2% female) (Table. 4 and Figure.4).

Table No.3: Frequency of Cutaneous Leishmaniasis in Area Wise

Area	Male	Female	Total	Male %	Female %
East	8	4	12	15%	7%
West	13	5	18	23%	9%
South	2	2	4	4%	4%
Central	4	3	7	7%	5%
Nisai	6	2	8	11%	4%
North	2	4	6	4%	7%

Figure No.5: Frequency of Cutaneous Leishmaniasis in Area Wise

The statistical data demonstrates that there are notable differences in infection between males and girls with infection and significance higher than females ($p < 0.05$). Age-wise, there are no appreciable differences between the age ranges of 0 to 10, 11 to 20, 31 to 40, 51 to 60, and 61 to 70 years ($p > 0.05$), but the age group of 21 to 30 years does differ significantly ($p < 0.05$). Arms are considerably higher in males than females ($p < 0.05$) compared to other body parts, such as the face, legs, and mixed. If we compared the districts of Muslim Bagh, West was considerably higher ($p < 0.05$) than the other villages.

Nearly 68% of males ($n=141$) and 32% of females ($n=66$) were confirmed to have cutaneous leishmaniasis overall. The illness affected people at a higher rate than any other age group: 24% in the 0–10 age range, 23% in the 21–30 age range, 17% in both the 11–20 and 31–40 age ranges, 9% in the 40–50 age range, and 5% in both the 51–60 and the 61–70

age ranges. Both sides' exposed body parts had widespread infections. The face showed the greatest percentage of infections (16% male and 13% female followed by the thighs (18% men, 7% women), the arms (19% men, 7% women), and the mixed body parts (15% men, 5% women). The samples from Balochistan showed the greatest prevalence rate of The next most gender-balanced provinces are Punjab (4% male, 4% female), Sindh (20% male, 6% female), Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (15% male, 6% female), and Cutaneous Leishmaniasis (34% male, 11% female).

The exposed body parts were where the bulk of the lesions were found. Additionally, patients with cutaneous leishmaniasis were discovered in nearly every district of the city. Younger individuals were more likely to contract the infection than children and the elderly.

4. DISCUSSION

In many tropical nations around the globe, leishmaniasis is an endemic disease. Most members of Asian groups come from underprivileged neighborhoods and lead subpar lifestyles. Such people are more likely to contract vector-borne diseases. Leishmaniasis is widespread, according to research, not just in Pakistan but also in India, Iran, Afghanistan, and China (Shaheen et al., 2020). The cited literature states that Pakistan has reported on extensive leishmaniasis research from 2003 to 2018 (Mostafavi et al., 2022).

Yousuf et al., (2021) reported more Cutaneous Leishmaniasis instances have been documented from the North West Frontier Province (NWFP) in children and young adults than in persons over the age of 60. They also claimed that men (60.5%) are more likely than women (39.5%) to have the illness. This study is consistent with the ongoing investigation because, as we saw, males were involved in 64% of the 207 cases examined while women were only in 36% of those cases. The ten-year gap between the earlier study and this one demonstrates the persistence of cutaneous leishmaniasis in Pakistan.

Different research from Lower Dir, Pakistan by Khan et al. (2021) discovered a substantial difference between cases of cutaneous leishmaniasis in men and women. This gender disparity may be caused by the fact that women are typically women are kept inside their homes while men leave to fulfil their duties in the workplace and in business. Infection was identified as an important skin condition in 24.5% of men but only 16.1% of women.

However, a previous study by Bhutto et al., (2009) discovered a small change between instances involving men and women. In fact, they investigated the entire country and found that the disease is most severe in the provinces of Sindh and Baluchistan. They claim that the province of Sindh has a significant amount of cases. The diagnostic process, which involved a smear test and the examination of skin lesions, was the same as the one we used in the current study investigation.

While evaluating the Cutaneous Leishmaniasis patients in Multan, Ahmad et al. (2022) stated that it is a neglected tropical disease. They found 198 patients with cutaneous leishmaniasis, 101 of whom were men and 97 of whom were women, with ages ranging from 10 to 40. In the current case, individuals between the ages of 21 and 30 years old were commonly diagnosed with skin lesions related to Cutaneous leishmaniasis. There may be a small variation in the gender and age distribution between the two regions as a result of environmental factors. Due to population density issues, 32% of the positive instances in the current investigation were only found in district West, while only 8% were found in South.

The province of Sindh continues to be a leishmaniasis focus. In a nationwide survey (Sharif et al., 2017), 94 Sindh province residents tested positive for the illness. The 102 patients whose data they collected represented every region in Pakistan. Leishmaniasis is without a doubt one of the most prevalent skin illnesses in Sindh, according to the literature. It is spreading rapidly and widely.

It appears that *T. indica* in Chabahar has not been particularly susceptible to the Leishmania parasite, or this rodent's biological characteristics have made it less susceptible to the parasite's spread. Another factor preventing this rodent from creating a nest deep enough for sand flies to successfully reproduce and increase their population to the point where they can serve as a helpful vector is a difference in the soil's texture.

Cutaneous leishmaniasis, one of Pakistan's most prevalent vector-borne illnesses, is linked to immunosuppressive conditions like HIV/AIDS, substandard housing conditions, migration, insufficient nutrition, and vector control failures. It mainly affects people with poor incomes. Skinny leishmaniasis cases have been recorded in Pakistan's urban-rural regions of Sindh and Punjab, Azad Jammu and Kashmir, and suburban areas of the Baluchistan province, especially in the native neighboring regions of FATA and KPK (Shaheen et al., 2020). Uninfected areas that border endemic regions are thought to be at risk, and one of the causes of Cutaneous leishmaniasis outbreaks is the colonization of big populations in areas where sandflies are common (Khan et al., 2021).

Here, we suggest applying some non-conventional pesticides to control the vector, particularly since adult flies are active from the final week of August until December and are plentiful then on their breeding grounds.

5. CONCLUSION

Cutaneous leishmaniasis is a main community health issue in many areas of the world. The illness is more prevalent in rural areas, among outdoor workers, and among visitors to endemic regions who do not take the proper measures. Combining several strategies can lower the chance of infection, including vector control, early diagnosis and treatment, public

awareness campaigns, and bettering living conditions and access to healthcare. Combinations of interventions that focus on the vectors and the humans are necessary for the effective prevention and management of cutaneous leishmaniasis. These include implementing public health education programmes to increase knowledge of the disease, using insecticides to control sandflies, and improving housing conditions. Anti-parasitic medications are frequently used to treat cutaneous leishmaniasis, however, depending on the parasite type and the patient's immune system, their effectiveness can vary. To eliminate the lesion in some circumstances, surgery may also be necessary. Overall, cutaneous leishmaniasis continues to have a big impact, so attempts to stop and manage the illness must be made. To lessen the effects of this ignored tropical disease, more study is required. New treatment options and preventative measures must also be developed.

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